

Computer-Assisted Instruction in Teaching Philippine Folk Dance

Submitted: 21.08.2021

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the impact of computer-assisted instruction (CAI) on the academic performance of the Bachelor of Physical Education (BPED) students in learning Philippine Folk Dance. The study involved two factors namely, (1) the pre-test-post-test factor and (2) the type of instruction given to the BPED students in learning Philippine Folklore tests. In assessing the effectiveness of CAI across the pre-test-post-test measures, the study utilized the quasi-experimental design and was carried out with 30 second year students taking up Bachelor of Physical Education in one of the state universities in Cebu. Data were analyzed by employing the mixed Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The results revealed that CAI pre- and post-test scores were portrayed as steeper increase inclines. However, this could not be interpreted as a significantly different or more effective mode than the traditional instruction.

Keywords: Computer-Assisted Instruction; Teaching; Philippine Folk Dance

INTRODUCTION

Over the years, the utilization of technology is progressively becoming a more essential part of education in facilitating and enhancing the teaching-learning process in different subject areas (Cummings et al., 2008). In the field of Physical Education (PE), the innovations of computerized gadgets and digital apparatus have been noticed all around the world as professionals utilize them for the evaluation and application of fundamental movement, assist the unification of fundamental movements with execution, expand formative assessment procedures, to obtain evidence of summative assessment for the performances of the learners and most especially technology is being utilized in giving instructions (Hay and Macdonald, 2010). Physical Education covers various topics including the Philippine Folk Dances. As everyone knows, it is a vital piece of the Philippine culture, and that it is the responsibility of every Filipino student to treasure and protect it. One way is to be educated to preserve and nurture this for the future generation.

According to DeKeyser (2015), The Theory of Skill Acquisition is about the systematic evolution of how a person learns and improves a range of skills. The creation starts with a basic understanding of how to technically execute a skill. In realistic situations, this theoretical knowledge would then allow a person to apply the expertise. As a result, this acquired activity will gradually become an autonomous ability by continuous practice, manifesting high-level competence, and effortlessness (Taatgen et al., 2008). One example of skill acquisition is learning dance. Bezen noted that in schools, dance education programs provide students with opportunities to develop critical thinking and analytical skills, cooperation and teamwork, self-expression and self-esteem, organization and problem solving, cultural literacy, and movement-based communication of emotions (Young, 2003). In dance education, emerging technology can

be implemented, not just to support conventional curriculum objectives, but also to provide students with new learning resources.

Dance classes strive not only to enhance the dance skills of learners but also to develop personal dancing features, self-trust, and ability to reflect creative capacity, so as to be able to achieve a far higher creative degree output. In the study of Lin et al. (2018), assessment using mobile technology is utilized from passive to active learning. Considering the effects of the approach on dance skills, self-efficacy, and learning enjoyment, 9 weeks of experimentation was performed. In terms of self-efficacy and learning satisfaction, students did better in the conventional approach to passive to active learning than those students in the traditional approach to teaching. Overall, the data revealed that students incorporating assessment using mobile technology and from passive to active learning approach exhibited better skills in dance than some of those students learning with the conventional flipped learning approach and traditional instruction.

Furthermore, due to advancement in technology, new teaching strategies and introduction of the new mode of learning, PE is subjected to be taught using computer-assisted instruction. Just as any educational platform, Physical Education (PE) is arising regarding coordinating Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into ordinary teachings (Kretschmann, 2015). However, according to Yang et al. (2019), the reasonableness of Physical Education (PE) instructing, the computer-assisted instruction (CAI) in physical education can develop understudies' realization through visible instructing. Literature proposed that there are a lot of good benefits and understudy can get upon integrating CAI in learning PE.

The use of CAI as the means of providing instructions to the students showed positive results on some aspects of learning especially on the academic regime of learning. However, in the field of physical education (PE), the practicality of teaching PE is performance-based and more on practical demonstration type of instructions (Yang & Zhao, 2019). In the study of Denardi & Correa (2013) the ballet student's skills showed an improvement in their performance over the traditional way of teaching. Hsia et al., (2019) also showed the same result, stating that in terms of dance skills students with technology-based instructions outperformed those who are learning with the traditional approach. However, according to Basturk (2005), even though scores and grades of students showed a more significant increase in CAI lecture, improvement of performance is due to concepts and practices backed with CAI. Still, studies on Computer-Assisted Instructions are limited and although these provide positive results these may also cause more problems in the future (Yang & Hwang, 2019). More studies are encouraged to identify emerging issues and the improvement of the effect of Computer Assisted instruction, especially on non-academic and practical subjects.

In most American schools, students struggling to achieve their highest ability are a concern ("The Underachieving Pupil", 2002). What educators can do to make sure that all the students they teach have met their fullest capacity and become good learners? In order to enhance all student successes, several schools are incorporating CAI into their curriculum (Patterson, 2005). More analysis is required to validate the investment of funds to introduce CAI as a potential way to improve student success. Also, a certain study of Tolbert (2015) scrutinized how computer-aided instruction (CAI) affects the students' accomplishment in a particular subject area and examined student discernment of the computer-assisted instruction. The study contrasts a classroom where traditional instruction and supporting computer-assisted instruction

were being utilized. The examination of the data shows that there is no notable distinction between the two types of instruction. According to the outcome of the study, research should be continued to be conducted on the impact of computer assisted-instruction in contrast to the traditional instruction.

Studies suggest that computer-assisted instruction (CAI) enhances the level of learning; in a shorter period of set-up, learners acquire equal quantities of knowledge as students that are instructed traditionally. Additionally, learners utilizing computer-assisted instruction (CAI) outperforms in maintaining learning level (Cotton, 2001). Through utilizing computer-assisted instruction (CAI), several studies have proved that students develop optimistic outlook rather than those of students that are instructed traditionally. Cotton (2001) highlighted that the whole main assumption arose via study results from influence in regard to computer-assisted instruction (CAI) on learner's behavior.

To meet the standards of modern education in this current generation, it is important to understand and comprehend the capabilities of online learning to enhance the quality of education. Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate if teaching Philippine Folk Dance with the use of computer-assisted instruction helps students achieve better in the subject compared to teaching Philippine Folk Dance in the traditional method and have a better attitude to Traditional Dances through the use of CAI.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study aims to assess the impact of computer-assisted instruction (CAI) on the academic performance of the Bachelor of Physical Education (BPED) students in learning Philippine Folk Dance. More specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

(1) What is the academic performance of the students under traditional instruction method?

(2) What is the academic performance of the students under computer-assisted instruction method?

(3) Is there a significant difference between computer-assisted instruction (CAI) method and the traditional instruction method in teaching and learning PH Folk dance?

(4) What relevant proposals can be made?

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter provides historical background on computer-assisted instruction and how the use of technology in education was utilized for teaching-learning purposes specifically in Philippine Folk Dances. It then lists the demands for effective integration of computer-assisted instruction as a revolutionary breakthrough in traditional instruction. The literature deals with the obstacles to the incorporation of computer-assisted instruction and then the opportunities for students, teachers, and the whole organization of computer-assisted instruction integration. Finally, the literature concludes by characterizing the link between computer-assisted instruction (as transformative innovation) and traditional instruction (as retaining innovation), if one eliminates the other or complements the other in educational settings.

Dance courses can offer students" awareness in their movements thus a good practice to develop their body -dances that include learning International and Traditional Philippine Folk Dances. According to the study of Blackler et al., (2019), literature recommends movement might be a helpful practice design to some individuals and one self's administration for exercise yet it is not utilized consistently. However, due to certain circumstances such as the introduction of online classes, learning folk dances is proposed to be taught using computer-assisted instruction.

You (2020) analyzed the present usage of internet technology in the area of dance and choreography was analyzed. To determine the result of learning online is the aim of this study. Further, the study develops dance education in integrating an approach that is competence-based provided the prerequisites in enforcing online programs. The result of the study is universal, meaning it can be used in international and local practices. You, (2020) the usage of internet

technologies are analyzed and aims to determine its impact on the students studying „Choreography and Dance). Therefore, he concluded that the developments of online dance training can be both applied to local and international management practices. But there is a need for improvement such as the training needs.

The study of Stevens & Huddy, (2016) gives emphasis to the evolution of the reflective pedagogy in teaching dance and it is based on collaboration, critical questioning, exploration, and connection in the community. Performance in Context Model (PCM), developed in integrating teaching practical dance skills, engagement of the community, and artistry. The marrying of teacher-as-performer, teacher-as-researcher, and teacher-as-artist are represented by the PCM and approaches were also emphasized in response to learning and teaching dances.

Technology incorporation in education altered methods by producing modern instructions and settings in the learning process through computers and application servers which add new facets to distance learning. On the other hand, these booming and advanced technologies provide fresh approaches to various areas, especially dance, that provide everyone interested in dance with a productive journey. The study of Gratsiouni et al. (2016) aimed to critically examine the way the Computer Based Learning-CBL YouTube network channels operate both as teaching resources and as a result of dance education like the traditional Greek dance in Karagouna. The data suggest that someone utilizing YouTube has an immersive and successful learning and teaching tool (dancers, dance instructors, etc.) if the particular person has past dance experience already.

In their study, Kico & Liarokapis (2019) revealed that from the recordings of the professional dancers, a huge back-projection system is needed to determine the effectiveness of

using technology in learning folk dance. The recordings of the professional dancers were compared by the captured movements of sixteen participants and conclude that augmented reality is useful in learning folk dance.

Based on the status of the Philippines, conducting computer-based learning is a challenge. A study conducted by Gradwohl (2018) seeks to help teachers in understanding the favorable circumstances and the drawbacks of utilizing innovation or computer-assisted instruction (CAI) in a dance classroom to show the twenty-first century-skills of innovativeness, basic reasoning, and coordinated effort. With this, the efficacy of integrating Computer-assisted Instruction in teaching Folk Dances is compared to the traditional way of teaching.

Gürbüz et al., (2018) stated that the outcomes of their study uncovered that the CAI was more successful in aiding the understudies build up the probability ideas than Traditional Instruction (TI). In accordance with integrating Computer-assisted instruction (CAI) in learning Philippine Folk Dances, researchers investigate if there is a significant difference in integrating computer-assisted instruction (CAI) between the traditional instruction (TI).

In the education field, computer-aided instruction, based on the theory of programmed instruction, promotes successful learning of concepts, stimulates excitement and curiosity for learners, encourages critical thinking, and offers direct feedback to learners. Bariham et al. (2019) conducted a study to explore the perception of CAI students in senior high school as teaching and learning tools, and if sexuality and school location influence students' adoption of CAI throughout social studies. Research data were collected from 3 Junior high schools randomly sampled from the North East Region of Ghana using the Slovin formula for the determination of sample size. The study found that students' perception of CAI was positive, but

their application of technology to learning was poor. And, male students used technology to learn more than female students. There had been no statistically significant gap in the incorporation of CAI in learning between rural and urban students.

In the study conducted by Singh (2018), the effectiveness between traditional classroom lectures and computer-assisted instruction was being compared and analyzed whether they have a significant effect on the synthesis skills of the students. Singh (2018) used Bloom's Taxonomy as support upon analyzing his major hypothesis where he hypothesized that there is no significant difference between students who belonged to the experimental group and students who were in the group of traditional instruction in terms of acquiring psychological attributes. In his study, it was proven that computer-assisted instruction is considerably effective in enhancing the application skills and cognitive performance of the students compared to the traditional classroom lecture. Learners who received treatment of computer-assisted instruction were also well-motivated and showed eagerness to learn. However, the learners' comprehension skills of those who belonged in the computer-assisted instruction group were barely not affected by the use of this instruction.

The study conducted by Lai et al. (2015) pointed out that computer-assisted learning has a notable advantageous impact on outcomes of both academic and non-academic of the students. The study contributes to the perception of the impact of computer-assisted learning on educational outcomes for unattended inhabitants in some of the developing countries. The study adds up as well to the perceptions of the impacts of computer-assisted learning through focusing on learning outcomes far from their respective scores on their tests. Aside from the effects of computer-assisted instruction involvement on the learners' scores on the tests, this study also investigated the effects on outcomes in terms to non-academic such as students' assertiveness and

attentiveness in learning. Moreover, learners with parents who were not able to finish their education can benefit more from the computer-assisted learning program.

The study of Tolbert (2015) scrutinized how computer-aided instruction (CAI) affects the students' accomplishment in a particular subject area and examined student discernment of the computer-assisted instruction. The study contrasts a classroom where traditional instruction and supporting computer-assisted instruction were being utilized. The study revealed that there is no notable difference gain and negative outlook on computer-assisted instruction. Based on the findings of the study, the main goal should be to examine students' academic performance in various units with the help of computer-aided instruction. Tolbert (2015) recommended that there's a need for school administrators and policymakers to be concerned because of the insufficiency of the difference in the result.

Integrating Computer-Assisted Instruction to a group of students who are into Traditional Instruction is a challenge. The transitions can result in hesitations to both the understudies and the administration as to what Instruction is competent enough for the learning of the students. With this, Barstuk (2005) conducted a survey to measure the scores between understudies in Lecture-plus-CAI to understudies in Lecture-only or Traditional Instruction. The survey used participants of identical midterm and last tests of the year scores and it showed that understudies in Lecture-plus-CAI sections got elevated scores on midterm and last tests of the year more than participants in the Lecture-only sections. This survey simply recognizes the efficacy of Computer-assisted Instruction based on the scores of the understudies. This means that computer-assisted instruction is competent enough on imparting knowledge to understudies.

In accordance with integrating Computer-assisted instruction (CAI) in learning Philippine Folk Dances, researchers investigate if there is a significant difference of integrating computer-assisted instruction (CAI) between the traditional instruction (TI). Furthermore, these relevant studies could be beneficial in solving the drawbacks of integrating computer-assisted Instruction.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researchers utilized the quasi-experimental (general linear model) design in order to assess the effectiveness of Computer-Assisted Instruction (CAI) across the pre-test-post-test measures. Quasi-experimental is a design that identifies a comparison group that is as close as possible to the intervention group in terms of baseline (pre-intervention) characteristics (White and Sabarwal, 2014). It is suited in the study because it aims to assess the effectiveness of teaching Philippine Folk Dance with the use of computer-assisted instruction and evaluate if students achieve better academically compared to teaching Philippine Folk Dance in the traditional method.

Research Environment

Figure 1. Map of Research Environment

This study is conducted in Cebu Normal University-Main Campus; a state university located at Osmeña, Blvd., Cebu City, Philippines with the grid coordinates of 10.3017° N,

123.8967° E. The institution is a state research university designated by the Commission on Higher Education as Center of Excellence. Cebu Normal University comprises three different departments namely the College of Teacher Education and College of Nursing Level 4 Accredited, and College of Arts and Sciences Level 3 Accredited. The two Departments (CTE and CAS) offer different degrees. The said environment is under the supervision of the Government which students officially enrolled are fully under the free tuition of any State University College (SUC). The respondents are coming from the College of Teacher Education under the program of Bachelor of Physical Education.

Sampling Design

a. Population

The targeted population of the study is the 2nd year students of Cebu Normal University taking up Bachelor of Physical Education. There are two blocks in this year level, specifically, Block A has 38 students and Block B has 38 students for a total of 76 students in this year level. With reference to the university's prospectus, in the first semester of the second year, the following students are enrolled in the subject Philippine Traditional Dances thus, are expected to give appropriate data necessary for the study.

b. Sampling Frame

Figure 2. Sampling Frame

c. Choosing Sampling Technique

The study follows a certain criteria in such a manner that the researchers made sure that 15 from the controlled group and 15 from the experimental group have nearly the same average which is 1.5 or above based on their grades last semester.

d. Determining of Sample Size

In determining the sample size, the researchers asked data from the registrar for the Dean's List as the basis for their academic performance. The researchers made sure that they are all in the upper class, that they belong to the top 30 students and have an average of 1.5 or above. The controlled group has 15 students and the experimental group would also have 15 students.

Research Instrument

This study utilized an adapted test questionnaire for the pre-test and post-test from the revised Licensure Exam for Teachers (LET) material by Vergara (2019). The instrument was validated and tested for its reliability. A 20-item with multiple choices will be used for eliciting

information from the target population. Among the instruments available online, the instrument from Vergara (2019) is the most appropriate one in measuring the operational definition of the construct in the study.

Data Collection

Figure 3. Data Collection Flowchart

First, the researchers made a letter of consent approved and signed by the research adviser for the key respondents. Afterwards, it was addressed to the chairman of the department for the final approval. The researchers then selected the potential key respondents to be in the Intervention Group and Controlled Group based on 3 criteria set by the researchers. Once the participants read the consent letter and agreed to participate in the study, they were gathered through messenger group chat for the giving of instruction and update purposes. Afterwards, a total number of 30 respondents were randomly picked and divided into two groups. The first

group consisted 15 respondents that were assigned to the Intervention Group with computer-assisted instruction (CAI) and the remaining 15 respondents were assigned to the Controlled Group specifically without the utilization of computer-assisted instruction (CAI). The researchers then gave the Intervention Group and the Controlled Group a pre-test of 20-items with multiple choices apart. After that, the researchers applied the lecture method for those respondents with computer-assisted instruction (CAI) and on the other hand, a module was given to the Controlled Group. After a successful lecture with computer-assisted instruction for the Intervention Group, a post-test was given to them to assess their academic performance in learning Philippine Folk Dance. Similarly, for the controlled group, after studying using the module material, a post-test was also given to them with a corresponding purpose as with the other group. After that, the researchers gathered the data acquired and then set in motion to data analysis.

Data Analysis

In analysing the data, researchers utilized the mixed Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The mixed ANOVA is a statistical test that intends to measure differences across combinations of within-subjects design and between-subjects design. Hence, the study involved two factors namely, (1) the pre-test-post-test factor and (2) the type of instruction given to the BPED students in learning Philippine Folklore tests. The model is illustrated below, indicating split-plot designs of the four possible conditions or sources of mean for testing the difference.

	<i>Pre-test</i>	<i>Post-test</i>
<i>Traditional Instruction</i>	CONDITION #1	CONDITION #2
<i>Computer-Assisted Instruction</i>	CONDITION #3	CONDITION #4

Using this approach, it determines if there was a main effect of the test period and type of instruction. The key effect is the effect of a single independent variable, which combines the other independent variables for all levels(s), the data analytic approach also helps researchers to assess if the two independent variables are interacting, and when the effect of one independent variable is greater at one level of the other independent variable than at the second level of the same independent variable, an interaction is present. All significant levels will be measured using a $p\text{-value} < .05$.

Ethical Consideration

Certain precautions were taken into account by the researchers to address the ethical considerations of the study. Bearing in mind the respondent's legal rights, all respondents were informed with total clarity of the essence of the study. The Informed Consent Form was distributed to each research respondent after explaining the study's aims and benefits. The researchers assured the respondents that participation is optional, and at any point, respondents are entitled to withdraw from the research. Throughout the study, confidentiality and independence are guaranteed to the respondents. Respondents were advised that all data gathered from them will be kept at the highest level of confidentiality.

RESULTS

Table 1. Pre- and Post-Test Performance of BPED Students in Learning Philippine Folk Dance using Traditional Mode of Instruction

	<i>M</i> (in average)	<i>SD</i>
<i>Pre-Test</i>	11.00	4.99
<i>Post-Test</i>	15.27	3.13
n=15		

Table 1 presents the pre- and post-test performance of BPED students in learning Philippine Folk dance in the Traditional Mode of Instruction. It is revealed that there is a relative increase in the post-test performance ($M=15.27$, $sd = 3.13$) of students from their pre-test performance ($M=11.00$, $sd= 4.99$).

Table 2. Pre- and Post-Test Performance of BPED Students in Learning Philippine Folk Dance using Computer-Assisted Instruction

	<i>M</i> (in average)	<i>SD</i>
<i>Pre-Test</i>	12.53	4.61
<i>Post-Test</i>	18.67	1.84
n=15		

A second group of pre- and post-test was conducted to measure the effectiveness of computer-assisted instruction in the learning of Philippine Folk Dance among BPED students. It

is revealed in table 2 that there was also a relative increase in performance in post-test scores (M=18.67, sd= 1.84) from the pre-test scores (M=12.53, sd= 4.61).

Table 3a. T-test Comparison of Post-Test Performance between of BPED Students in Learning Philippine Folk Dance

	<i>t-test</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>decision</i>	<i>interpretation</i>
<i>CAI-Post – TI-Post</i>	3.63**	.000**	Reject H_o	Significant
<i>CAI-Pre – CAI-Post</i>	-6.74**	.000**	Reject H_o	Significant
<i>TI-Pre – TI-Post</i>	-6.15**	.000**	Reject H_o	Significant

****Significant at $p\text{-value} < .01$**

By independently comparing the results of scores of all conditions, table 3a reveals significantly difference results. It is shown in that there is a significant difference in the performance post-test scores of BPED students in Computer-assisted instructions (CAI) and traditional instruction (TI), $t(23)=3.62$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, suggesting that students in CAI scored significantly higher than those in the TI. Also, there is a significant difference in the CAI Pre- and Post-test performance scores, $t(23)=-6.74$, $p\text{-value}=.000$. This further suggests that the post-test scores in the CAI group are significantly higher than that of the pre-scores. This may imply that there is a significant effect of CAI to the learning of Philippine Folk Dances. On a similar note, there is also a significant difference in the pre- and post-test scores of those in the traditional instruction $t(23)=-6.15$, $p\text{-value}=.000$. This indicates that there is a significant increase of scores after the traditional instruction treatment. Also, this may imply that using traditional

instruction has a significant effect to the learning of Philippine Folk dances among the BPED students.

Table 3b. Test of Within-Subjects Test (Comparison between Pre- and Post-Test Scores and Interaction Effects)

Multivariate Tests ^a							
Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Pre-test-Post-test	Pillai's Trace	.747	82.695 ^b	1.000	28.000	.000	.747
	Wilks' Lambda	.253	82.695 ^b	1.000	28.000	.000	.747
	Hotelling's Trace	2.953	82.695 ^b	1.000	28.000	.000	.747
	Roy's Largest Root	2.953	82.695 ^b	1.000	28.000	.000	.747
Pre-test-Post-test* CAI-Traditional	Pillai's Trace	.087	2.664 ^b	1.000	28.000	.114	.087
	Wilks' Lambda	.913	2.664 ^b	1.000	28.000	.114	.087
	Hotelling's Trace	.095	2.664 ^b	1.000	28.000	.114	.087
	Roy's Largest Root	.095	2.664 ^b	1.000	28.000	.114	.087

^a**.significant at p-value<.01

The results of the Two-Way Mixed ANOVA showed that there was a significant main effect of period of assessment towards the post-test performance scores of BPED students in learning Philippine Folk Dances, $F(1,28)=82.695$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, $\eta^2=.747$. The results further reveal a large effect size of period of assessment towards the increase post-test scores. However, there was no significant interaction between the period of assessment and type of instruction,

$F(1,28)=2.664$, p -value=.114. This indicates that the type of instruction may not have anything to do with the increase in the post-test scores across the Computer-Assisted Instruction and Traditional Instruction.

Table 3c. Test of Between-Subjects Effects (Comparison Between Computer Assisted Instruction and Traditional Instruction Scores)

<i>Source</i>	<i>Type III Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>Partial Eta Squared</i>
<i>Intercept</i>	12384.067	1	12384.067	500.607	.000	.947
<i>Grouping</i>	91.267	1	91.267	3.689	.065	.116
<i>Error</i>	692.667	28	24.738			

To check whether the type of instruction has significant main effect towards performance scores of the BPED students learning Philippine Folk Dances, a test of between-subjects effects was conducted and shown on Table 3c. The test revealed that the type of instruction did not yield significantly different test results in the pre- and post-test performance scores of the BPED students, $F(1,28)=3.689$, p -value=.065. This suggests that the type of instruction (e.g. CAI and TI) may not have significant influences in the learning of Philippine Folk Dances.

Table 3d. Estimated Marginal Means of the Interaction between Type of Instruction and Pre-test-Post-Test

		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>95% Confidence Interval</i>	
				<i>Lower Bound</i>	<i>Upper Bound</i>
<i>CAI</i>	<i>Pre-Test</i>	12.533	1.240	9.993	15.073
	<i>Post-Test</i>	18.667	.662	17.310	20.023
<i>TI</i>	<i>Pre-Test</i>	11.000	1.240	8.460	13.540
	<i>Post-Test</i>	15.267	.662	13.910	16.623

It is revealed in Table 3d that both modes of instruction yield an increase of post-test scores, MCAI=18.667; MTI=15.627, from a reference pre-test scores. However, it cannot be established that the increase from pre- to post-test scores can be accounted for by the difference in the mode of instruction. An illustration of the trend of scores is reflected in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Estimated Marginal Means

DISCUSSION

The primary purpose of this study was to assess the impact of computer-assisted instruction (CAI) on the academic performance of the Bachelor of Physical Education (BPED) students in learning Philippine Folk Dance. In our study, the students under traditional instruction method showed positive improvement in their academic performance. This result is identical to a study where significance of having the presence of a teacher in the teaching-learning process is being highlighted in a study conducted by Anderson et al. (2001) and Siemens (2002) where the traditional source of information becomes a facilitator of knowledge and the student turns from being a learner who is passive to a learner who becomes active.

On the other hand, students under computer-assisted instruction (CAI) method also revealed increased performance in their academic performance. This is congruent with the study conducted by Sutyasadi and Suharti (2010) claimed that students can be assisted in their self-study program by utilizing Computer Aided Instruction (CAI). As long as the student has their own hardware and software, the study program can be made possible whether in their respective homes or in dance studios. Through directing some self-study tasks, the students can possibly boost the time taken to attain the expected competencies.

Our results indicate no significant difference between computer-assisted instruction (CAI) method and the traditional instruction method in teaching and learning PH Folk Dance. The outcome of this study is not different from the study conducted by Tolbert (2015) entitled "The Impact of Computer-Aided Instruction on Student Achievement". The study scrutinized how computer-aided instruction (CAI) affect the students' accomplishment in a particular subject area and examine student discernment of the computer-assisted instruction. The study contrasts a classroom where in traditional instruction and supporting computer-assisted instruction was being utilized. The examination of the data shows that there is also no notable distinction between the two types of instruction. In any case, classrooms that are using traditional learning or instruction utilizing pen and pencil, controlled by the teacher with longer time duration and studies using Computer Assisted Instruction are equivalent with each other. It shows no significant difference and that neither of the two instruction has a learning advantage. It is recommended that what accounts for the advantages of learning CAI in this study and others is the better quality instruction using CAI Materials (Fletcher-Finn & Gravatt, 1995). The study was consistent with the findings of Clinkscates (2002) that "Both methods have positive features that bring the best out of instruction".

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In addition to contributing to the research body investigating the impact of CAI, the present study showed that learning in both Computer-Assisted Instruction and Traditional Instruction can be both effective given the relative increase of post-test scores. As to the determination of which mode is more effective, there is no significant statistical finding that suggests a more effective method. While the trajectory of the CAI pre- and post-test scores are portrayed as steeper increase inclines, this could not be interpreted as a significantly different or more effective mode than the traditional instruction. Hence, this evidence demonstrates that both methods can be independently effective insofar as instruction to Philippine Folk Dances among BPED students are concerned.

Additional measurements in future studies are highly recommended; since the present the study was designed to focus on learning Philippine Folk Dance by 2nd year BPED students drawn from a single university, future studies should widen gathering of data and selection of variables to other public institutions and other private institutions for high quality and generalizable data. To better meet BPED students' assessment learning needs, apart from giving modules and online lecture, diverse instructional strategies can be employed, and may incorporate diverse demo scenarios and examination questions. Further empirical studies should be carried out on the use of computer-assisted instruction purposes, on different areas and at different levels to provide a sound basis for the integration of technology in teaching and learning Physical Education courses. Last, since the BPED students had a positive impression of utilizing CAI in learning Philippine Folk Dance, we recommend that this instructional approach be extended to Physical Education courses evaluating diverse performance, to enhance BPED students' learning willingness and acquisition of skills in those contexts as well.

In conducting the study, researchers were not convinced by anything that would just achieve personal benefit in conducting analysis only to finish the report without observing the correct procedure and methods. Nothing has been traded for personal gain to distribute truthful outcomes. The researchers adhere to the research ethical consideration that it is immoral to obtain a request to manipulate the study results.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bakogianni, S., Kabakli, E., Karkou, V., & Tsakogianni, M (2007). Teaching Traditional Dance using E-learning tools: Experience from the WebDance Project. *The arts for wellbeing.*
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228846393_Teaching_Traditional_Dance_using_E-learning_tools_Experience_from_the_WebDance_Project.
- [2] Basturk, R. (2005). The Effectiveness of Computer-Assisted Instruction in Teaching Introductory Statistics. *Educational Technology & Society*, 8 (2), 170-178.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/220374763_The_Effectiveness_of_Computer-Assisted_Instruction_in_Teaching_Introductory_Statistics
- [3] Bariham, I., Muchiri, M. M., Ondigi, S., & Kiio, M. N. (2019). Senior High Schools' Students' Perception Of Computer-Aided Instruction In North East Region Of Ghana. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies (IJIRAS)*, 6(8).
https://www.academia.edu/40303206/Senior_High_Schools_Students_Perception_Of_Computer_Aided
- [4] Blackler, A., Desai, S., Swann, L., Chamorro-Koc, M., Moyle, G., & Stephens, M. (2019). Using technology to enhance and encourage dance-based exercise. *Heliyon*, 5(3), e01241.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e01241>

- [5] Gürbüz, R., Dogan, M. F., & Dede, Y. (2018, February). The Role of Computer-Assisted Instruction in the Teaching of Probability. (3), 1-18. 10.16986/HUJE.2018036943
- [6] Denardi, R. A., & Corrêa, U. C. (2013). Effects of instructional focus on learning a classical ballet movement, the pirouette. *Journal of dance medicine & science : official publication of the International Association for Dance Medicine & Science*, 17(1), 18–23. <https://doi.org/10.12678/1089-313x.17.1.18>
- [7] Dekeyser, R. (2007b). Skill acquisition theory. In B. VanPatten & J. Williams (Eds.), *Theories in second language acquisition: An introduction* (pp. 97-113). New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.
- [8] Fletcher-Finn C., & Gravatt B. (1995). The Efficacy of Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI): A Meta-Analysis. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.2190/51D4-F6L3-JQHU-9M31>
- [9] Gradwohl, A. K. (2018). Perceptions of Technology in Dance Education: the Effect of Technology on Student Learning and Teaching Strategies of the Twenty-First Century Skills in Dance Education. *Scholarship & Creative Works at Digital UNC*. <https://digscholarship.unco.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1123&context=theses>

- [10] Gratsiouni, D., Koutsouba, M., Venetsanou, F., & Tyrovola, V. (2016). Learning and Digital Environment of Dance – The Case of Greek Traditional Dance in Youtube. *European Journal of Open, Distance and E-Learning*, 19(2), 80-95. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1515/eurodl-2016-0009>
- [11] González, A. Turning a traditional teaching setting into a feedback-rich environment. *Int J Educ Technol High Educ* 15, 32 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-018-0114-1>
- [12] Kico, I. & Liarokapis, F. (2019). A Mobile Augmented Reality Interface for Teaching Folk Dances. *VRST 19: 25th ACM Symposium on Virtual Reality Software and Technology*, 1-2. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3359996.3364752>
- [13] Kretschmann, R. (2015). PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS' SUBJECTIVE THEORIES ABOUT INTEGRATING INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY (ICT) INTO PHYSICAL EDUCATION. *TOJET: The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology* 14 (1). https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1057351.pdf?fbclid=IwAR2D1w2S9HhuZvLnd_ZXIkxD1onmIK3LnAWFJRIFOJKJXu4UIfuZy6c0
- [14] Lai, F., Luo, R., Zhang, L., Huang, X., & Rozellea, S. (2015, August). Does computer-assisted learning improve learning outcomes? Evidence from a randomized experiment in migrant schools in Beijing. *Economics of Education Review*, 47, 34-48. <https://fsi->

[live.s3.us-west-1.amazonaws.com/s3fs-public/lai-et-al-2015-computer assisted learning.pdf](https://live.s3.us-west-1.amazonaws.com/s3fs-public/lai-et-al-2015-computer_assisted_learning.pdf)

[15] Lin, Y., Hsia, L., Sung, M., & Hwang, G. (2018). Effects of integrating mobile technology-assisted peer assessment into flipped learning on students' dance skills and self-efficacy. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 27(8), 995-1010.

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/10494820.2018.1461115?journalCode=nie20>

[16] Lu-Ho Hsia, Gwo-Jen Hwang & Chi-Jen Lin (2019). A WSQ-based flipped learning approach to improving students' dance performance through reflection and effort promotion, *Interactive Learning Environments*, 0:0, 1-16.

[10.1080/10494820.2019.1651744](https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2019.1651744)

[17] Qi-Fan Yang, Chi-Jen Lin & Gwo-Jen Hwang (2019) Research focuses and findings of flipping mathematics classes: a review of journal publications based on the technology-enhanced learning model, *Interactive Learning Environments*, 10.1080/10494820.2019.1637351

[18] Singh, P. (2019). A comparative study to evaluate the effectiveness of traditional classroom lecture versus computer assisted instruction at senior secondary level. *International Journal of Physiology, Nutrition and Physical Education*, 4(1), 96-100.

<https://www.journalofsports.com/pdf/2019/vol4issue1/PartC/3-2-296-666.pdf>

- [19] Stevens, K. & Huddy, A. (2016). The Performance in Context Model: A 21st Century Tertiary Dance Teaching Pedagogy. *Research in Dance Education* 17(2), 67-85. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14647893.2016.1178714>
- [20] Sutiyasadi P., & Suharti, T. (2010). Implementation of Interactive Computer Aided Instruction in Learning of Javanese Traditional Classic Dance. *International Journal of Mechanical and Mechatronics Engineering*, 4(6). <https://zenodo.org/record/1335252/files/15014.pdf>
- [21] Taatgen, N. A., Salvucci, D. D., & Borst, J. P. (2008). Threaded cognition: *From multitasking to a new theory of skill acquisition*. *PsycEXTRA Dataset*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/e527312012-141>
- [22] Taie, M. (2014). Skill acquisition theory and its important concepts in SLA. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 4(9). <https://doi.org/10.4304/tpls.4.9.1971-1976>
- [23] Tolbert, Ernest Jr., "The Impact of Computer-Aided Instruction on Student Achievement" (2015). *Education Dissertations and Projects*. 127. https://digitalcommons.gardner-webb.edu/education_etd/127
- [24] Yang, J., & Zhao, Z. (2019). Development and implementation of computer assisted instruction system in physical education based on ASP.NET technology. *International*

Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET), 14(13), 145. <https://online-journals.org/index.php/i-jet/article/view/10712>

- [25] You, Y. (2020). Online Technologies in Dance Education (China and Worldwide experience). *Research in Dance Education*, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14647893.2020.183297>